

Energy and Economic Growth

Applied Research Programme

Energy system development pathways for Ethiopia - PATHWAYS

WP1.2. Energy Supply Pathways for Ethiopia: workshop report

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January 2020

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Acknowledgements: The workshop was funded by the UK Department for International Development's (DfID) Energy and Economic Growth programme (EEG), which is managed by Oxford Policy Management Limited (OPM).

1 Introduction

On the 27th August 2019, a one-day workshop was held in Addis Ababa by University College London (UCL) and the Policy Studies Institute (PSI) to discuss future energy pathways for Ethiopia.

The workshop was part of the ‘*Energy System Development Pathways for Ethiopia*’ (Pathways) project. The Pathways project aims to enhance modelling capabilities in Ethiopia to support the development of energy system development pathways for Ethiopia in a context of rapidly increasing demand for energy. The project will develop qualitative storylines for future resource development and address knowledge gaps on how demand for electricity, including electricity for productive uses and demand side policies might affect energy system development pathways. The research team is led by UCL and include PSI, the Addis Ababa Institute of Technology (AAiT) and the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH). The Pathways Project is funded through the Energy and Economic Growth applied research programme, which is funded by the UK’s Department for International Development (DFID) and managed by Oxford Policy Management (OPM).

The first stage of the Pathways project is to derive supply-side development pathways for Ethiopia. This involves developing – together with stakeholders – qualitative storylines for energy resource in Ethiopia. To support the development of the scenarios, a literature review was carried out by PSI, with support from UCL, and an expert workshop held in Addis Ababa to inform the qualitative storylines. This report provides a summary of the discussions that were had at the expert workshop (see Annex A for the workshop agenda).

The aim of the workshop was to support the development of qualitative storylines for future resource and capacity development in Ethiopia in the medium to long-term (i.e. 2025-2050). The workshop set out to discuss two key questions:

1. What do different energy supply pathways for Ethiopia look like?
2. What is driving / will drive change in Ethiopian energy supply?

A total of 18 participants attended the workshop, largely from government but also from donors and the private sector in Ethiopia¹.

1.1 Introduction to the Workshop

The workshop began with a welcome by the organisers and a round of introductions by organisers and participants.

Dr Julia Tomei (UCL) introduced the Pathways project, including the EEG programme and the project team. She described the project aims and objectives, methods used and expected outputs. She set out the aim of the workshop and emphasised the importance the Pathways project placed on stakeholder engagement. She was followed by Mr Oliver Broad (UCL) who provided an introduction to energy pathways and scenarios. He began by setting out what is meant by an ‘energy system’ i.e. which includes supply, transmission, distribution and demand, as well as behaviours and emissions. He then placed these concepts into the local context using a diagram to represent Ethiopia’s energy balance and highlighting its current dependence on woody biomass which is primarily used for cooking. He described how energy systems are reliant on technologies, the future of which is characterised by dynamism, complexity and uncertainty, and how models provide one way of dealing with this complexity. Mr Broad provided examples of narratives for energy pathways, highlighting key differences and drivers in each. He finished with a diagram that

¹ The workshop was attended by representatives of the following organisations and institutions: Ministry of Trade and Water; Ministry of Water, Irrigation and Electricity; Environment, Forest and Climate Change Commission; Ethiopian Energy Authority; Ethiopian Electric Utility; SNV, Ministry of Mining, Petroleum and Natural Gas; and, Blue Flame Gas.

illustrated progress towards delivery of Ethiopia's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), which sets out efforts to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

2 Brainstorming the Issues

Having set out the project and research background, a brainstorming session followed during which participants were asked to identify key issues affecting energy supply in Ethiopia (see Photo 1). The addition, and name, of each new category was discussed and agreed with all participants. Where strong feelings remained as to the need to split themes, the underlying reasons for the split were examined and new categories were added as appropriate.

Photo 1. Results of the brainstorming session.

During the break, the issues and categories were organised into a number of overarching Themes (see Table 1). Seven of these themes were initially identified, but due to restrictions in numbers of participants and facilitators, this was reduced to six following a group discussion. The six themes were: 1) technology; 2) policy and institutions; 3) resources and environment; 4) markets and finance; 5) global, regional and local context; and, 6) stakeholders and capacity.

Table 1. Key issues for Ethiopia’s energy supply identified during the brainstorming session.

Theme 1	Theme 2	Theme 3	Theme 4	Theme 5	Theme 6	Theme 7
Technology	Policy & institutions	Resources & environment	Markets and finance	Global, regional & local context	Stakeholders & capacity	Energy Access
<p>Knowledge in technology construction</p> <p>ICT</p> <p>Old infrastructure, technology & investment</p> <p>Absence of clean technology</p> <p>Dependence on hydroenergy supply</p> <p>Energy technology used</p> <p>Regional autonomy</p> <p>Geosituation</p> <p>Centralised vs decentralised generation</p> <p>Energy efficiency and conservation</p> <p><i>Quality, affordability, accessibility of technologies and ease of use</i></p>	<p>Power sector reform</p> <p>Weak and old policy</p> <p>Planning/ policy</p> <p>Problem with energy conservation strategy</p> <p>Energy policy and government priority</p> <p>Policy issues and off-grid energy to hold with private sector</p> <p>Government attention to energy sector</p> <p>Focus only on power generation, lacking energy saving</p> <p>Policies to enable innovation</p> <p>Absence of risk guarantee for private sector</p>	<p>Waste to energy</p> <p>Availability of biomass for different uses</p> <p>Alternative energy issues e.g. biogas, biomass, ethanol</p> <p>Policy of green resilience economy</p> <p>Dependence on hydropower</p> <p>Renewable energy technologies</p> <p>Poor assessment of RETs</p> <p>Fossil energy use</p> <p>Climate change and environmental issues</p> <p>Indoor air pollution and women</p> <p>Low awareness of negative impacts of unsustainably</p>	<p>WTP and households</p> <p>Tariff reforms</p> <p>Finance and investment</p> <p>Per capita income/ GDP per capita</p> <p>Economic growth and impact on demand</p> <p>Foreign currency shortage</p> <p>Low off-grid investment</p> <p>Market barriers</p> <p>Models for market planning</p> <p><i>Poor distribution of improved cookstoves</i></p> <p><i>Accessibility and end user role in energy</i></p>	<p>Regional energy markets and East Africa Power Pool</p> <p>Different topography to supply energy in different areas of the country</p> <p>International cooperation</p> <p>External influence (e.g. Nile River conflict)</p> <p><i>Refugees</i></p>	<p>Low awareness of energy utilisation, efficiency and conservation</p> <p>R&D</p> <p>Technology & human capacity</p> <p>Employee skills and capacity</p> <p>No energy audit in the energy consuming industries</p> <p>Knowledge barriers</p> <p>Low awareness of new technology for energy supply</p> <p>Capacity for developing new technology</p> <p>Low awareness of negative impacts of unsustainably harvested/ burnt biomass</p>	<p>Refugees</p> <p>Poor distribution of improved cookstoves</p> <p>Accessibility and end user role in energy</p> <p>Gender</p> <p>Tier of energy access</p> <p>Household energy transitions and behaviour</p> <p>Quality, affordability, accessibility of technologies and ease of use</p> <p>Dependence on biomass</p>

<p><i>Tier of energy access</i></p>	<p>Institutional strength</p> <p>R&D</p> <p>Gender mainstreaming</p> <p>Poor structured set up of energy sector</p> <p>Green resilience economy</p> <p>Energy efficiency and conservation</p>	<p>harvested/ burnt biomass</p> <p><i>Dependence on biomass</i></p>	<p><i>Household energy transitions and behaviour</i></p> <p><i>Quality, affordability, accessibility of technologies and ease of use</i></p> <p><i>Tier of energy access</i></p>		<p>Social acceptance e.g. land and hydro</p> <p>(Poor) coordination of stakeholders in energy sector</p> <p>Private sector involvement to build capacity</p> <p>Experience sharing</p> <p>Networking problem within government and private sectors</p>	
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3 A Deeper Dive

The next exercise was dedicated to enabling a deeper dive into the six themes identified during the brainstorming session. Participants were split into three groups of equal size and each group was allocated two of the six themes (see Photo 2). Discussions of each theme were limited to 30 minutes and were moderated by two members of the project team from UCL and PSI. Reporting was ensured by one of the two moderators, as well as one of the participants taking notes in a structured format (see Annex B).

Photo 2. Small group discussions

This exercise was designed to focus on four specific questions: first, to provide an opportunity for a deeper dive into each theme with the objective of highlighting important energy system drivers that they contained; second, to elaborate on chosen drivers and clarify their meaning; third, to relate the drivers within each theme to a description of the current state of play within the Ethiopian energy system; and fourth, to discuss what opportunities or barriers would be involved in changing this status quo and designing a different future for the country. The following paragraphs offer a structured summary of this output. Summaries of the discussion for each theme are provided below, with more detailed notes provided in Annex B.

3.1 Theme 1: Technology

Energy technology is necessarily at the heart of all future energy pathways for Ethiopia. The consensus among participants however was that current levels of knowledge in both the development and the construction of different energy technology systems is weak. Domestic manufacturing of energy technology is not developed and the country therefore relies heavily on imports as the de facto strategy. This applies both to technology and to expertise. This knowledge gap inevitably spreads wider across the energy sector leading to a low capacity in terms of systems operation and a clear gap in domestic energy related research.

When asked about the structures that underpin energy technology, participants highlighted that a heavy reliance on government-led developments and investment was undermining growth in the energy sector: levels of investment are currently too low and the financial structure that surrounds the sector does not

incentivise the involvement of private actors. While international donor finance is currently available for Ethiopia, the overall picture remains one of insufficient investment.

These low levels of investment were considered particularly important in the context of an ageing infrastructure that is expensive to maintain, and especially given low local knowledge and capacity. Levels of investment in new options were also seen as important for a system where the dominant energy form remains hydropower. While historically a reliable and stable source of power, hydro systems are increasingly seen as a risk due to their vulnerability to climate change. They also represent an important source of maintenance as they age or are subject to, for example, siltation. On the positive side, participants consider Ethiopia's high levels of renewable energy resource to represent a true opportunity for the country to diversify supply and increase reliability.

In addition to low levels of investment, participants noted that the current energy technology market is fragmented. While they were highlighted in other themes as key to supporting future energy pathways in the country, obtaining the rights to develop and operate an off-grid energy system remains ad hoc. This institutional barrier is linked to the low number of private sector organisations that currently operate in this way. It spreads to include a lack of both regulation and robust technical standards around the sale of stand-alone energy technology. An example was given for solar lanterns, for which the presence of informal market participants opens the system to low quality products. Ultimately, there is no legal framework by which technology development capabilities and appropriate standards can be realised.

Looking ahead, a focus on enablers and characteristics of future systems brought forward clear suggestions for change in relation to energy technology. In particular, participants highlighted the need for technology transfer to take place more efficiently and more widely with a focus on local production. One key example for this transfer would relate to adequate and improved cookstoves. This approach would require deeper public- private collaboration and partnership around technology development with a need for governmental and development institutions to work with the private sector to help unlock investment in the domestic energy market. This may mean refocusing current incentive systems that currently strongly support other parts of the economy such as e.g. food production and the agricultural system.

3.2 Theme 2: Policies and Institutions

Multiple drivers, and related challenges, were cited under this theme. For instance, participants discussed the government's focus on power generation, which meant other issues (e.g. energy conservation, transport, innovation) were overlooked. Participants suggested that the focus on generation rather than e.g. energy savings by end users, had been a contributor to load shedding in Ethiopia. While power sector reform was provided as a driver of energy system change, many participants commented on the poor structure of the energy sector, particularly its fragmentation, which led to administrative, market and other inefficiencies.

The lack of private sector involvement in policy design (both on and off-grid) was highlighted by participants as a challenge for the energy sector. They argued that while the private sector was sometimes involved in the final 'verification' of a policy, there was little inclusion of sectoral needs and ideas in the design. One participant argued that this may be due to a lack of experience of engagement with the private sector. As a result, current incentive mechanisms were not fit for purpose and access to finance and markets, as well as enabling environments were lacking. They commented that while some donors (e.g. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)) and NGOs (e.g. GIZ) were supporting the government to create enabling environments, current initiatives did not go far enough. One participant also raised the question of what happened when donors and NGOs left or a programme finished.

Policy design and institutional capacity were also cited as a challenge, particularly at regional and woreda levels where there are few local practitioners and capacity is low. It was suggested that civil servants

needed extensive training on energy issues, including specifically on energy technologies. Better policy documentation, including availability in languages other than Amharic and English, would improve regional knowledge of energy policy. Similarly, participants identified a need for greater investment in local authorities.

Also on institutions, participants discussed the politicisation of (energy) policy, wherein directors were appointed on political grounds, rather than on merit. This meant that many directors lacked technical knowledge of the policy domains over which they had authority. Participants argued that only top-level officials were currently involved in policy formulation, but that energy experts and practitioners should be involved at an early stage. The need for greater private sector involvement was again highlighted.

When asked about changes required to policies and institutions, participants focused on the opportunities for energy efficiency. This included greater availability of energy efficient appliances and technologies, import incentives on renewable energy technologies other than solar, and introducing standards for energy efficient technologies. This latter point was considered crucial for avoiding negative perceptions of energy efficient technologies due to the availability of low-quality products on the market.

3.3 Theme 3: Resources and Environment

Ethiopia's dependence on two key energy sources – water (for hydropower) and biomass (for cooking and heating) – was widely discussed by participants. On hydropower, participants expressed concern about the country's current reliance on hydropower, particularly in a context of climate change which would see reduced water availability. On biomass, participants highlighted the negative impacts of biomass in contributing to deforestation and indoor air pollution, which it was noted particularly affected women. It was acknowledged that biomass could also create rural businesses, generate employment and income through tree planting, charcoal production, cookstove production. Yet these opportunities were not yet recognised by government who were focused on electricity and urban areas. Carbon credits were discussed as a way to incentivise forest conservation, promote climate resilience and the green economy.

Strategies to promote the use of ethanol in transport were mentioned as a way to decarbonise the transport sector. One participant noted that Addis Ababa alone would require 30 million litres of ethanol per year, but that the country's sugarcane plantations and mills were not yet completed. Once finished, the country's 10 sugar mills were expected to be able to produce ~300 million litres per year, which would be distributed across the country.

The role of policy and planning in supporting the use of alternative energy sources was also discussed. Participants highlighted a lack of knowledge about the availability of different energy sources, such as biogas, and how to exploit them. This was related to the absence of an integrated energy plan, one that would cover all aspects of the energy system – not just electricity supply, but also demand-side issues. Energy models were agreed to be important tools to support energy planning in Ethiopia. However, participants described a shortage of skilled manpower, a lack of energy standards, information gaps, weak financial incentives and a lack of government support for non-conventional energy sources which hindered energy planning. Furthermore, the lack of cooperation between ministries working on e.g. energy and environment, was highlighted, which constituted a major barrier to change.

In terms of future opportunities, the importance of a move away from biomass was considered key, especially since population growth represented a threat to energy supply. The National Electrification Programme (NEP) aims to deliver access for all by 2030 but requires a mix of energy sources and technologies to reduce dependence on biomass. Increased involvement of the private sector, particularly in off-grid areas, was required, but this required a supportive policy framework. Participants concluded that there was an urgent need for energy planning that would consider all supply-side options, as well as on and

off-grid electricity was considered vital. Participants argued that further research was required, which used and applied modelling tools, for planning, resource management and implementation.

3.4 Theme 4: Markets and Finance

Providing energy firms with access to functional markets and to cheap and reliable sources of finance has been considered key in supporting the development of the future energy system of the UK. When taken in the context of Ethiopia, this thematic area was immediately broadened to include clear references to income, purchasing power, and willingness to pay the cost of a new energy system investments. Households, and in particular their different characteristics in rural and urban areas, are strong actors able to generate tangible support for specific technology changes. This ability is however doubly limited by national economic growth: its proper distribution is linked to purchasing power, and its proper investment could lead to higher grid reliability. Both aspects will affect household uptake of new and efficient technology as they relate to their ability to either purchase or actually use the technology.

Economic growth in Ethiopia is currently related to the development of the manufacturing sector. Its low levels are however considered to represent a key barrier to progress and investment in the energy sector with current governmental budgets facing the choice of trading off reliable food supply and investment in larger infrastructure projects. The corollary of low investment in energy infrastructure however is that high levels of reliable energy supply are not available to support a growing industrial sector.

On a macro level, a key underlying barrier to positive change in the relationship between market finance and the energy sector in Ethiopia is perceived to be a general lack of institutional capacity that is preventing the development of “Energy as business”. Financial institutions currently expect faster returns than energy projects are able to provide and do not see these investments as the long-term, stable, development opportunities that they are. This typically leads to reduced promotion of energy projects and a lack of interest and/or understanding among potential shareholders. This is not irremediable however and higher levels of government collaboration with these institutes could help bridge this gap.

3.5 Theme 5: Global, Regional and Local Contexts

Against a backdrop of an increasingly interconnected world, the role that different regional contexts play in the design of a national energy system are becoming progressively more important and interdependent.

The diversity of local geography and its impact on the specific local contexts is of particular relevance in Ethiopia. The country’s high central plateau sits at altitudes that vary between 1290 and 3000m elevation, it is divided in two by the great rift valley and slopes to the lowlands in both the north west and south east of the country. These stark topographic differences are linked to a wide range of variations in climate from hot desert conditions all the way through to monsoon or subtropical highland conditions. These, in turn, will have important impacts on both local demand and corresponding energy system design.

This diversity was recognised by participants who transformed the original focus of the theme to include local contexts and highlighted the importance of investigating the role of decentralised and regional systems. These would, in part, acknowledge the variations in renewable energy potential across the country. While participants noted that this energy potential is well understood, they highlighted that plans for its development on a regional and local scale were not. Part of this gap is related to low knowledge and capacity in terms of regional and decentralised systems.

The question of regional energy systems spread beyond domestic regions and brought forward the larger question of considering Ethiopia’s energy system in the context of its neighbouring countries and of the East African Power Pool (EAPP). While trade links are supposedly at the top of the energy agenda, the national strategy has yet to be completed. While it was agreed that the country’s priority should be to

supply domestic demand first, participants agreed that energy trade would have a beneficial impact and delays were linked to important barriers in terms of governance, finance, and politics. These same reasons have affected larger project developments like e.g. GERD.

Looking to solutions, participants believed that incentives should be sought to stimulate the role of the private sector. As highlighted under Theme 4, there was a perceived need to start viewing energy investments as business opportunities. While international aid programmes currently exist to support these investments, they are insufficient and do not address structural barriers. Energy technology is currently imported at high cost rather than produced locally. Heavy taxation has been lifted through five-year schemes in other sectors of the economy, but applying these changes to the energy sector raises governance and institutional responsibility issues. Fostering an environment where international technology manufacturers are welcomed to Ethiopia is nevertheless seen as an essential step in establishing learning, creating employment and setting up domestic supply chains that could accelerate energy development at local, regional, national and international levels.

3.6 Theme 6: Stakeholders and Capacity

Under this theme, participants discussed the roles and perceptions of different stakeholder groups within Ethiopia. Public acceptance of energy infrastructures was discussed in relation to land use and hydropower with an example given of how local opposition to an energy project was successful in seeing it relocated. Participants discussed the need for greater awareness raising amongst the public, but cautioned that low electricity tariffs limit public interest; indeed, under the current tariff reform, the poorest consumers will not see increased tariffs. They argued that the public were more responsive to price than quality of electricity supply, or any other factor affecting supply.

The role of the Ethiopian Energy Authority (EEA) in energy efficiency and demand side management was mentioned by participants. The EEA promotes these through media, meetings and training but this had not yet been effective. Low tariffs also mean industry does not take ownership of efficiency improvements and many electric motors need replacing. Participants argued that the government did not yet pay sufficient attention to the energy sector.

When asked about future changes, participants thought a more cost-reflective tariff would lead to greater private sector involvement, as well as higher quality power supply. It was also suggested that a privatised energy system could increase public involvement due to higher tariffs. Participants thought social and environmental impact assessments could also be used to engage the public, but cautioned these would need to be robust and transparent.

Participants again highlighted poor coordination between stakeholders (prime minister's office, the Ministry of Water, Irrigation and Energy (MoWIE), EEA, Ethiopian Electric Power Corporation (EEP), the utility, private sector, organised civil society); for example, affecting which technologies that enter the market. Finally, participants suggested a detailed energy audit of the industrial sector was required.

4 Ranking the Drivers

Following lunch, participants reconvened in two groups to undertake the penultimate exercise, which was to rank the drivers listed under every theme. The aim of this exercise was to identify those drivers the participants thought were most important in the short (i.e. to 2025) and longer-term (i.e. to 2050). Groups were asked to identify up to three drivers for each time period and discussed all six themes.

Photo 3. Ranking the drivers

The groups were again moderated by two members of the research team and notes taken. The results were then fed back in plenary and the results shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Ranking of drivers affecting Ethiopia’s future resource pathways

Theme	Group	Driver Ranking (2025)	Driver Ranking (2050)
Technology	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality, affordability, accessibility of technologies and ease of use Energy efficiency and conservation Improved infrastructure (distribution and generation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart systems and ICT (to support implementation and management of energy systems) Centralised and decentralised generation Diversified energy mix
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficiency and conservation Energy mix i.e. diversified Private sector involvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production, construction and installation of technologies Investment in technology Technology for renewable energy
Policies & Institutions	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address poor institutional arrangements (increase institutional strength), fragmentation, lack of cooperation and stability Availability of updated policies – continuous revisions, supported by evidence e.g. databases Strong private-public partnerships e.g. to address risk guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies to create innovation and R&D, including within local institutions Willingness to incentivise investment in the energy system Appointment on basis of merit not politics
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of policy consistency e.g. enabling a diversified energy mix Institutional arrangement for internal coordination/ poor organisational structure across public sector organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder and private sector engagement Government too focused on power generation and lack of attention to energy savings and energy conservation Sector coordination (fragmented offices)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentives for energy efficient technologies 	
Resources & Environment	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of RETs, including biodiesel, solar, to avoid GHG and increase energy access Feasibility studies, including at regional potential for RETs Reduction of biomass (for cooking) to protect natural resources, through increased awareness of RETs and discourage use of biomass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stronger focus on environmental protection to reduce dependence on hydropower (resilience to climate change) No biomass for cooking (with positive impacts on household air pollution and women) Skilled manpower in all aspects of energy systems
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need for government to create awareness on knowledge of resources and how to exploit them More involvement from private sector Skilled manpower 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dependence on hydropower and climate change affecting availability of water – need diversified energy mix Strengthened energy standards and legal frameworks to keep up with changes in the system Focus on energy NOT electricity
Markets & Finance	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued tariff reforms to attract more private sector investment Studies of market barriers Resolve foreign currency shortage to attract private investment in energy sector => currency convertibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greater local production and markets for energy with a strengthened private sector – off-grid investment Household energy transitions and behaviours leading to energy access for all and higher energy demand (with energy efficiency measures) – off-grid investment Job creation in the energy sector due to economic growth
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Models for market planning Off-grid investments/ quality of equipment Tariff reforms – grid and off-grid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic growth Impact on/ of job creation Household energy transitions and behaviours
Global, Regional & Local Context	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feasibility studies of local resources, energy economics to support energy generation at the local level to support comparison of selling energy to domestic vs regional markets Capacity building from federal to local level to support institutional capacity Tax exemptions for RETs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralised energy generation, distribution, transmission => greater regional autonomy Stronger negotiating skills within East Africa and beyond – capacity building Greater investment opportunities, including green manufacturing
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource assessment first at the national level Co-financing for green energy development, especially at the regional level Knowledge gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional energy markets Creating investment opportunities for both domestic and international investors Excessive concentration on hydro will affect regional energy supply
Stakeholders & Capacity Building	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strength and coordination through an energy sector platform/forum to create greater organisation Technology and capacity development strengthened by 2025 with development of stronger institutions through training awareness raising and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased government investment in R&D and SMEs Creation of greater social acceptance through community funds.

		<p>staff retention (greater pay and salary reforms)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a Ministry of Energy 	
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination between all stakeholder – all active stakeholders • Low regulations from the standards authority must improve/change • Clear roles and responsibilities on key issues for energy sector, e.g. dedicated energy and conservation authority. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for energy efficiency • Research and development • Technology and human capacity – building local content.

At the end of the discussions, and before creating their own scenarios, workshop participants were asked to vote for the theme that they considered to be the most relevant for the future of the country. Participants voted once only with a majority of votes being cast for Theme 2 (Policy and Institutions), closely followed by Theme 4 (Markets and Finance).

The final exercise was for participants, in groups of 2-3 people, to develop future energy scenarios for Ethiopia. Drawing on the workshop discussions on current and future drivers of Ethiopia’s energy system, each pair was also asked to reflect upon:

- What will Ethiopian energy supply look like in 2050?
- What energy sources will be used?
- What technologies?
- Which actors?
- What outcomes?
- What milestones
- Emissions and greenhouse gases?
- Is the future positive or negative? Why?

Each group was then asked to present their scenarios in plenary (see Photo 4). Six scenarios were presented which captured a broad array of issues, many of which reflected the discussions that had taken place during the workshop. These are summarised below:

Energy sources. The role of fossil fuels was discussed in all the scenarios, with most envisaging low to no contributions. Nuclear was considered a clear risk that should be avoided by all but one group. The vulnerability of hydropower was heavily highlighted. While this was seen as introducing system resilience risk, most scenarios still expected this source to continue to dominate the system in 2050, followed by solar power and wind. All scenarios noted the need for a diversified energy system citing high levels of identified renewable potentials for solar, wind and geothermal in Ethiopia.

Transmission and distribution. By 2050, full electrification had been achieved in most scenarios through off-grid, decentralised and regional grids and technologies. Some groups see this happening as early as 2025. The integration of Eastern Africa into one electricity system was expected to support sustainable economic development by facilitating electricity exports and allowing economic growth. For one group, the objective was to reduce the country’s dependence on energy imports while ensuring that it is able to supply neighbouring regions in abundant, clean, and reliable electricity.

GHG emissions. Sustainability of the future energy system was a key feature of all contributions. Future systems rely systematically on high levels of renewable power. As a result of a diversified and low fossil fuel energy mix, GHG emissions were reduced and Ethiopia’s climate change targets achieved.

Photo 4. Presenting future energy scenarios for Ethiopia

Co-benefits. Health was an important driver for improving energy services, as was the creation of jobs which was at the heart of the energy transition. One group believed reduced poverty would be a given due to full electrification. Another considered that informal and traditional uses of biomass would be significantly reduced.

Policies and Institutions. One scenario highlighted problems with low stakeholder coordination and poor planning, while another mentioned the lack of involvement of the private sector. This was expected to change, with future support provided by stable national and regional energy institutions with higher levels of commitment and better coordination. One group envisaged a future that relied on the development of a green economy to exploit Ethiopia's renewable energy potential. The sustainability of the future energy system was also reliant on energy efficiency, with policy examples focusing on energy efficiency labelling, energy recovery and household efficiency. Ultimately, all groups highlighted the central role that government, NGO, private sector and financial institution actors had to play in providing structural support for this ambitious energy transition. Delivering this vision relied, for some, on power sector "unbundling" reforms, a strong role for privatisation and deep institutional change.

For most participants, developing the scenarios was a new exercise with some commenting that it was the first time they had thought so far ahead about the energy system. As a result, the scenarios were similar between groups and shared a common ambition for a clean, sustainable, reliable energy system. Among the groups there were few considerations of a more pessimistic future. Much of the output was a statement of where the country would end up rather than an explanation of how they expected the country might (i) get there or (ii) diverge along the way. This highlights the need for continuing engagement with stakeholders on energy futures, and further capacity development activities.

5 Workshop Close

The workshop was closed by Dr Sied Hassan (PSI) who thanked everyone for their attendance, participation and enthusiasm throughout the day. Dr Hassan stressed the importance for the Pathways project that it continued to engage with and be informed by the participants in order to ensure the research, outputs and outcomes were relevant to and useful for all stakeholders. The UCL team also expressed their gratitude to the participants and reiterated what a useful and informative workshop it had been.

Annex A Energy Pathways for Ethiopia Workshop Agenda

Date: 27th August 2019

Venue: Jupiter International Hotel, Cazanchis, Addis Ababa

Organisers: University College London (UCL), United Kingdom, and Policy Studies Institute (PSI), Ethiopia.

TIME	CONTENT
0800 – 0900	Arrival and refreshments
0900 – 0905	Housekeeping (including ethics)
0905 – 0925	Introductions and two key questions for the day: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are different energy supply pathways in Ethiopia? 2. What is driving/ will drive change in Ethiopian energy supply?
0925 – 0945	Introduction to the Pathways project, WP1.2, workshop objective and workshop agenda
0945 – 1015	What are pathways and scenarios? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pathways, scenarios and modelling • What do we mean by ‘narrative driver’? • How have they been used? • Setting the boundaries? Q&A
1015 – 1045	Brainstorming on key issues affecting energy supply in Ethiopia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issues mapping - Clustering into themes
1045 – 1115	<i>TEA/ COFFEE BREAK</i>
1115 – 1130	Group discussion on issues mapping <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which themes to discuss in groups? - Additional themes - does the group want to involve them or not?
1130 – 1230	Three group discussions (I) on themes, to identify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breakdown into constituent parts (i.e. narrative drivers) • How things are now: who (institutions)? What (works/ what doesn't)? Why (status)? • Opportunities and barriers
1230 – 1300	Each theme to feedback to group on drivers identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of drivers • Remove duplicates to produce a refined list of drivers
1300 – 1400	<i>LUNCH</i>
1400 – 1440	Rank drivers in order of importance (H/M/L) to (i) 2025 and (ii) 2050
1440 – 1450	Discussion on linkages between drivers
1450 – 1520	Small groups (2-3) to develop future scenarios based on drivers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What will Ethiopian energy supply look like in 2050? • What energy sources? • What technologies? • What actors? • What outcomes?
1520 – 1535	Feedback from each groups
1535 – 1545	Reflections, final comments and next steps
1545	<i>CLOSE</i>

Annex B Energy Pathways for Ethiopia Workshop Small Group Discussions ‘Annex title’ style

Theme 1. TECHNOLOGY	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge in technology construction • ICT • Old infrastructure, technology & investment • Absence of clean technology • Dependence on hydroenergy supply • Energy technology used • Regional autonomy • Geosituation • Centralised vs decentralised generation • Energy efficiency and conservation • Quality, affordability, accessibility of technologies and ease of use • Tier of energy access
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart grid to incorporate electricity production from diverse sources at diverse scales. • Domestic technology research
Section 2 How things work today	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic energy technology development is weak. The country relies on imported technologies and is therefore dependent on foreign countries. • There is limited domestic expertise in energy infrastructure construction and systems operation. • Investment in energy technologies is weak. Currently there is a reliance on the government, due to a lack of incentives for the private sector to get involved. • The energy technology market is fragmented. Obtaining the rights to develop and operate an off-grid energy system is ad hoc – currently have a few private sector organisations that operate in this way. The sale of stand-alone energy technology lacks regulation. There are informal market participants, and thus market is open to low quality products. • Robust technical standards are lacking. • There is no legal framework by which technology development capabilities and appropriate standards can be realised.
Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <p>Positive</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The realisation of technology transfer. There is a demand for this. • Local production of improved cook stoves. • Private sector and development institutions work together to enable investment in technology and domestic technology development capacity • Public-private partnership in technology development <p>Negative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biotechnology does not receive support from the government because focus is primarily elsewhere. • Government fails to incentivise private investment in technology and systems infrastructure (e.g. absence of tax incentives). Focus given to agriculture not given to energy sector technologies.

Theme 2. POLICIES AND INSTITUTIONS	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<p>Power sector reform</p> <p>Weak and old policy</p> <p>Planning/ policy</p> <p>Problem with energy conservation strategy</p> <p>Energy policy and government priority</p> <p>Policy issues and off-grid energy to hold with private sector</p> <p>Government attention to energy sector</p> <p>Focus only on power generation, lacking energy saving</p> <p>Policies to enable innovation</p> <p>Absence of risk guarantee for private sector</p> <p>Institutional strength</p> <p>R&D</p> <p>Gender mainstreaming</p> <p>Poor structured set up of energy sector</p> <p>Green resilience economy</p> <p>Energy efficiency</p> <p>Energy mix</p> <p>Poor institutional arrangements at a regional and woreda level – need for investment in local institutions</p> <p>Poor organisational structure at the federal level</p> <p>Lack of communication among stakeholders</p> <p>Lack of consistency in policy documents</p> <p>Lack of availability of policy documents leads to a lack of policy knowledge</p>
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p> <p>Poor policy documentation, including availability in languages other than Amharic and English.</p> <p>Political delegation to authorities e.g. directors, whose appointment is on political grounds rather than merit. Lack of technical know-how of the policy domains over which they have authority.</p> <p>Policy design is problematic, particularly at regional levels where there are no local practitioners and low regional capacity. Need extensive training on energy issues, including detailed knowledge on technologies. Current government efforts are not enough to meet needs.</p> <p>Low private sector involvement in policy design. Sometimes the sector is involved in final verification of a policy, but there is little inclusion of private sector needs and ideas in policy design. Although policy may say the sector is involved in design (e.g. cookstoves), current incentive mechanisms don't work – access to finance, markets, lack of enabling environments etc. Donors (UNDP) are working to create an enabling environment, but ultimately it is the government's responsibility and it doesn't go far enough. While government recognises the importance of the private sector, there is an issues with implementation possibly due to a lack of an implementation strategy.</p> <p>Lack of experience with private sector engagement (i.e. due to previous government monopoly). While donors are facilitating this interaction, more needs to be done. There is some private sector involvement, but it is technology dependent – good on geothermal.</p> <p>Poor structure of the energy sector leads to inefficiencies due to fragmentation.</p>
Section 2	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p>

<p>How things work today</p>	<p>Government focus on power generation to a greater extent rather than energy saving at the end user level has led to load shedding.</p> <p>NGOs involvement is coming to the forefront on energy issues e.g. GIZ support for capacity building, but what happens when NGOs leave?</p> <p>At the time of policy formulation, top level officials are involved only; however, it should go down at the expert level and even has to go deep into practitioner level at the time of policy formulation.</p>
<p>Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers</p>	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <p>Availability of energy efficient technologies</p> <p>There should be an incentive to import energy efficient technologies. There is a gap in the implementation stage</p> <p>Some technologies have tax incentives, e.g. solar, but this is not true for other renewable energy technologies. This acts as a barrier to importers and investors.</p> <p>Energy efficient bulbs are promoted, but there should be incentives for other energy efficient household appliances e.g. for cooking (injera)</p> <p>The private sector is not involved in policy formulation, rather during validation and the sector needs to be involved earlier.</p> <p>Fragmentation of offices, which leads to inefficiencies and poor management</p> <p>There needs to be a greater focus on demand and supply</p> <p>Cheap appliances are available, but they can be low quality and lead to high energy consumption with negative impacts on end users and affecting the perceptions of energy efficient technologies.</p>

Theme 3. RESOURCES AND ENVIRONMENT	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<p>Waste to energy</p> <p>Availability of biomass for different uses</p> <p>Alternative energy issues e.g. biogas, biomass, ethanol</p> <p>Policy of green resilience economy</p> <p>Dependence on hydropower</p> <p>Renewable energy technologies</p> <p>Poor assessment of RETs</p> <p>Fossil energy use</p> <p>Climate change and environmental issues</p> <p>Indoor air pollution and women</p> <p>Low awareness of negative impacts of unsustainably harvested/ burnt biomass</p> <p>Dependence on biomass</p>
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p> <p>Indoor air pollution caused by use of biomass</p> <p>Dependence on hydropower; climate change to affect the availability of water</p> <p>Deforestation</p> <p>Transportation sector uses fossil fuels, creating dependency on petrol imports. Some plans/ strategies to use ethanol in transport in Addis, but challenges with implementation and sugarcane plantations are not yet complete. Addis will require supply of 30 million litres of ethanol per year. Once finished, 10 finished sugarcane mills will produce 300 million litres per year which will be used around the country.</p> <p>Resource mix/ planning – there is no knowledge of what exists and how to exploit it e.g. biogas</p> <p>There is no integrated energy plan (i.e. beyond electricity), nor consideration of demand-side issue.</p> <p>Carbon credits could provide an incentive to promote climate resilience, green economy, and forest conservation (Min Env has responsibility for addressing deforestation)</p> <p>Models are important to plan in an organised way</p>
Section 2 How things work today	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p> <p>There is a shortage of skilled manpower</p> <p>The policy framework is designed to exploit indigenous energy resources</p> <p>No energy standards and no legal framework to guide energy use</p> <p>Weak government support on financial incentives</p> <p>Lack of government support for energy technologies (finance, incentives, information gaps).</p> <p>Making a fuel is a business and needs to be promoted: biomass production generates employment and business through tree planting, charcoal production, cookstove production e.g. the government is working on electric stoves for cooking. There are some initiatives, but they are not enough. 25 million families are using improved cookstoves, this is a real business opportunity, which is not currently recognised by government who only focus on electricity.</p>
Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <p>The role of the private sector needs to increase, especially in off-grid areas and requires a supportive legal framework.</p>

On biogas, information gaps mean that while prefabricated, underground biogas chambers are able to reach more people there is no government support and a lack of awareness. The private sector is working with government to raise awareness. There has been a US\$6 million investment from China and the US to increase the use of biogas in both on and off-grid communities.

Government needs to create awareness amongst people, for example by using media and social media.

No cooperation between ministries working on e.g. energy and environment. Duties are fragmented across three ministries, with little potential for change.

Focus on electricity, not broader energy use - especially biomass. There is a need to target rural people.

Population growth is a risk to energy supply and Ethiopia needs to shift demand from traditional biomass and promote the use of improved cookstoves/ use of modern energy i.e. electricity and gas. Fuel availability requires planning: electricity, on and off-grid, biogas etc.

NEP aims to deliver access for all by 2030, but requires a mix of technologies to reduce dependence on biomass. Promotion of private sector in the off-grid settings is required, as well as the involvement of other actors. This requires a clear policy and strategy.

Research has to be done using or applying modelling tools, for planning, for resource management, and implementation.

Theme 4. MARKETS AND FINANCE	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic growth and impact on demand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Income sensitive o Purchasing power increase o Shifting to modern energy - Level of development
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Affordability - Capacity of institutions - Job creation - Infrastructure development - Affordability and willingness to pay: the capacity of society and individuals to buy a technology - Households as a strong actors fofr generating demand for technology – particularly in rural areas - This is linked to job creation and income: their increase links to higher use of utilities and increase in demand - Demand for electricity is therefore strongly linked to income (GDP/capita) and to purchasing power - This requires accessibility of the technology
Section 2 How things work today	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impact on rural / urban infrastructure - Level of development - Manufacturing growth - Economic growth leads to higher grid reliability making additional equipment in households possible – this again is related to purchasing power. - National economic growth matters – budgets are currently limited and need to provide food as well as energy technology.
Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic growth and investment - Development of energy as a business - Importing - Economic growth: large industries require high levels of energy. This is something that the government is currently unable to respond to, which creates the need for private power sector investment. - Barriers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Energy needs to be developed as a business. o There is a knowledge and awareness gap around this within financial institutions o Stakeholders lack the understanding that this is not a direct profit system, rather a long-term investment. o There is a lack of promotion of energy projects – which is in part linked to a lack of knowledge relating to energy renewable energy technology o The impact of rural areas using biomass is not well understood. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Solar mini-grids are not profitable ▪ Households do not have the income to pay for the systems and there is a lack of government support. ▪ Needs to be more collaboration between government and financial institutions to bridge this gap.

Theme 5. GLOBAL, REGIONAL AND LOCAL CONTEXT (expanded to also include local)	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional / decentralised assessment and utilisation of resource potential so as to increase the supply in order to export to the neighbouring countries. - Addition to table: off grid energy
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Off grid – not well organised for supply of clean energy per specific reasons - High cost of transmission – mini grids at regional and local levels lead to different mixes
Section 2 How things work today	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy: east Africa – installation of T&D import and export
Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge gap and capacity issues on the local / regional energy potential - Autonomy of energy resources and administration / dissemination of energy across regions and out of the country (federalism issues) - With regards to the regional energy markets well managed domestic demand against export is not undertaken - Government willingness to open energy sector to the private sector which will help to have excess energy supplied to other neighbouring countries and regional power pool - Tx exemption for green manufacturing from international community and providers - Well documented energy potential assessments should be done at a country level - Creating investment opportunities like letting energy efficient technology investments tax break for some time which will incentivise investment. <p>OB notes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barrier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Knowledge gap and recognition that could be solved by a different planning approach o Links to the autonomy of regional governments and of the generation system - Policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Trade is still not available – the strategy is still not complete o GERD is faced with governance issues as well as financial and political elements - Targets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Government vision – there should be a priority to supply domestic demand first rather than exporting o This vision suffers from lack of financial capacity and should therefore rely on incentivising the role of the private sector more strongly. o The system is heavily reliant on hydro-power and is highly vulnerable to climate change as well as standard problems of e.g. siltation o There are alternative options, even if they are currently costly, they include geothermal, wind, or even waste to energy.) - Other notes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Electrification programmes exist within the WB and the IMF – and others – but are insufficient. o The focus also needs re-centring: the continued use of biomass is considered a problem by NGOs from a climate rather than an energy perspective. o Energy technology is high-tech and is not produced locally through lack of capacity. Solar power technology for example is imported. The government should support foreign manufacturing companies setting up in Ethiopia, employ local people and produce locally. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ This creates local investment and local private sector activity ▪ It also has the potential to bring in foreign currency.

- Mechanisms for 5 year tax breaks exist in other sectors of the economy and need to be extended to the energy sector. There is a question as to the complexity of the process and as to the governance institutions involved (e.g. Ministry of customs is responsible for the tax breaks on imports, but MoWIE is responsible for energy)
- Tax exemptions on technology import should be a number one priority. This could be followed by loans with low interest rates and other collateral systems
- This should lead to a green manufacturing focus at the core of finance supplied to the private sector and in parallel with donor organisations and NGOs to plug the gap.
- Land could also be provided in support of these private enterprises.
- Knowledge gaps for analysing the investment opportunities in relation to the energy potential that is clearly documented remain a big problem.

Theme 6. STAKEHOLDERS & CAPACITY	
Brainstorming items Initial drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low awareness of energy utilisation, efficiency and conservation • R&D • Technology & human capacity • Employee skills and capacity • No energy audit in the energy consuming industries • Knowledge barriers • Low awareness of new technology for energy supply • Capacity for developing new technology • Low awareness of negative impacts of unsustainably harvested/ burnt biomass • Social acceptance e.g. land and hydro • (Poor) coordination of stakeholders in energy sector • Private sector involvement to build capacity • Experience sharing • Networking problem within government and private sectors
Section 1 Further details	<p><u>What do these drivers mean, what other elements to they contain?</u></p>
Section 2 How things work today	<p><u>What is the current state of play: who is involved, what do they do, how do they do it, what works, and why?</u></p> <p>Stake/Equity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public acceptance influences large energy infrastructure development, e.g. local opposition to proposed location of project succeeded in relocation. • Low electricity tariff limits public interest. Under the current tariff reform, poorest consumers did not see increased tariffs. • Industry do not take ownership of efficiency improvements due to low tariff. Motors need replacing. • Not enough focus on the energy sector from the government. <p>Capacity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EEA promotes energy efficiency and DSM, through media, meetings, and training, but this has not been very effective. • Public have seemed more responsive to price than quality. They want cheap energy. Under current awareness, price may trump other considerations (e.g. source).
Section 3 Opportunities & Barriers	<p><u>What would positive, negative, or desirable change look like for these drivers?</u></p> <p>Positive</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination between all stakeholders (prime minister’s office, public, private sector, MoWIE, EPP/EEU/EEA, organised civil society) • Cost-reflective tariff leading to more private sector involvement. • Privatised energy system might increase public involvement due to higher tariff. • Cost-reflective tariff leading to quality power supply. • Detailed energy audit of industry sector. • Creation of jobs. Promoted and enabled accordingly. • Robust social environmental impact assessments that adequately engage the public. Transparency. <p>Negative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsustainable, poor quality power supply. • Poor coordination between stakeholders shapes the energy system (e.g. technologies that enter the market).